

Institutional Quality and Foreign Direct Investment Inflow in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper investigates the effect of institutional quality on foreign direct investment (FDI) inflow in Nigeria, using the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) econometric technique of analysis to capture the dynamic relationship between the variables and six indices of institutional quality were used. The paper finds that the rule of law, control of corruption, political stability and absence of violence, regulatory quality and government effectiveness have a short-run positive and significant effect on FDI inflow in Nigeria. In contrast, voice and accountability have a negative and significant effect on FDI inflow. Also, political stability and absence of violence, rule of law and control of corruption have long-run positive and significant effects on FDI inflow in the country. The findings further reveal that institutional quality indices and FDI inflow have a long-run relationship in the country. The paper concludes that institutional quality is a key determinant of attracting FDI inflow in Nigeria. The paper recommends that political stability and absence of violence, rule of law and control of corruption should be further strengthened in enhancing FDI inflow to the country; regulatory quality and government effectiveness should be improved on to sustain enhancement of FDI inflow in the short run and its positive direction in the long run; and voice and accountability should be encouraged to raise the hope of foreign investors to invest heavily in the country.

Keywords: Institutional quality, FDI inflow, short run, long run, Nigeria

JEL Code: E02, F35, F32, F2

1.0 Introduction

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflow is strong and the ultimate driver of global economic development, particularly in developing countries. Nigeria is characterised by limited resources, which inhibit the country from emancipating its economy from rampant unemployment and abject poverty. Khan *et al.* (2023) posit that developing countries are dwelling in limited resources, and huge capitals are needed to advance the development process. FDI inflows are essential to fill the funding shortage in developing countries, therefore, the attraction of FDI into the region should receive significant effort in the countries.

One of the factors that sustain attraction of FDI is institutional quality, as it was opined that pull of FDI inflows is a stimulant for economic development, and further assert that sustainability and determinant of attraction of FDI inflows in recipient countries goes along with countries with strong institutional quality (Polyxeni & Theodoreb, 2020).

It was revealed that institutional quality stimulates FDI inflows in developing countries (Behera *et al.*, 2020). Adegboye *et al.* (2020) assert that one of the main determinants of FDI inflow to recipient countries, particularly sub-Saharan African countries, is institutional quality, and a key driver of development in developing countries is FDI inflows.

Kahsai *et al.* (2011) assesses the effect of institutional quality on FDI in forty-five sub-Saharan African covering 1996 to 2007, using panel data and find that institutional quality exhibits an insignificant part in enticing FDI inflow into the region. They conclude that abundant natural

resources and raw materials are key in attracting FDI inflow rather than institutional quality. Qamruzzaman (2023) studies the influence of institutional and environmental quality on FDI inflows and finds that institutional and environmental quality had a substantial impact on FDI inflows. It was further revealed that the attraction of greater volumes of FDI inflows is central to strong environmental and institutional quality.

The nexus between FDI inflows and institutional quality varies in diverse economies, contingent on the structure of institutions in a country. There is a need to examine the type of connection between FDI inflows and institutional quality in Nigeria for better policy making in the country. This paper studies the effect of institutional quality on FDI inflow in Nigeria, covering 1996 to 2023.

This study is organised into five sections. Section two informs the nature of the relationship in the literature, methodology is addressed in section three, section four presents findings and interpretation and the conclusion is provided in section five.

2.0 Literature

Qamruzzaman (2023) examines the connection among FDI inflows, institutional quality and environmental quality in Lower-Income nations. He shows that institutional quality plays a substantial role in attracting greater FDI inflow to Lower-Income countries and finds that more FDI are attracted to countries with a high degree of environmental regulations, pollution management and sustainable resource practices. Adegboye *et al.* (2020) examine the significance of institutional quality on the nexus between FDI and economic development, covering 2000 to 2018 and using random and fixed effect techniques. They find that institutional quality is a major factor that drives FDI inflows, but the attraction of FDI through the quality of institutions

undermines the development of domestic investment and the underutilization of domestic resources in the region. Layla *et al.* (2020) investigate the dynamic association between FDI inflows and institutional quality between 1986 and 2016 using panel ARDL and reveal that institutional quality weakly influences FDI inflows in South Asia and strongly in South East Asia. They further reveal in their study that institutional quality is robustly important to stimulate FDI inflows in Southeast Asia, while a weak regulatory system hinders FDI inflows in South Asia because there is in public work lack of transparency and accountability in these countries. Fuzhong and Guohai (2023) examine moderating and mediating effects of institutional quality on FDI inflows in forty-two G20 countries covering 2005 to 2020, and reveal that institutional quality fascinates FDI inflows by hastening industrial structure optimization, inspiring technological innovation and growing trade openness in mediating analyses while natural resources abundance, tax level and financial development moderate direct connection between institutional quality and FDI inflows. Though financial development and natural resources reinforce the stimulating function of institutional quality in fascinating FDI, but the process was weakened by tax level. Saha *et al* (2022) assess the influence of institutional quality on FDI inflow for the period 2002 to 2018 and using GMM and threshold analysis. They reveal that regulatory quality and control of corruption aggravate FDI inflow, but voice and accountability, as well as the rule of law, mitigate FDI inflow in the economies. Their result also reveals that political stability and government effectiveness have an insignificant effect on FDI inflow. They also show that per capita GDP exceeds the 7.197 threshold level for regulatory quality to have positive impact on FDI while 7.776 threshold level for per capita GDP should be attained before voice and accountability would have direct influence on FDI in Lower-Middle income countries.

Lee (2021) investigates the threshold values of institutional quality on FDI inflows in thirty-four developing countries between 2000 and 2017, using GMM and finds that FDI inflow is positively influenced when the institutional quality is above the threshold level, but the reverse is the case when it falls below threshold level in the study area. He concludes that the countries will attract more FDI inflows when institutional quality is upgraded above a threshold level. Khan *et al.* (2023) examine the influence of institutional quality on sectoral FDI in Pakistan, covering the period 1986 to 2019 and use the ARDL technique. They find that FDI is positively and significantly influenced by institutional quality in the country. They also report in their study that sound institutional quality enhances huge transfer of technology through FDI and stimulates the economic performance of the countries. Kaushal (2021) investigates the nexus between FDI inflows and institutional quality in India for the period 2008 to 2018 using the augmented gravity model and finds that institutional quality had a positive effect on FDI inflows. He also shows that macroeconomic factors and institutional quality are key in enticing FDI into the economy. Dobrowolska, Dorożyński and Kuna-Marszałek (2021) reveal a positive association between FDI inflow and institutional quality in European Union member states. Polyxeni and Theodorb (2020) investigate the nexus between FDI inflows and institutional quality in Turkey between 2002 and 2017 using time series and panel analysis and find that institutional quality indexes, except government effectiveness, had a positive effect on FDI inflows. Sabir et al (2019) examine the effect of institutional quality on FDI inflows in low, middle and high-income countries between 1996 and 2016 using GMM and show that FDI inflows are positively affected by institutional quality. They also find that institutional quality had greater influence on FDI inflows in developed countries than developing countries. Kwaw-Nimeson and Tian (2023)

examines the connection between institutional quality and FDI and find that reform in institutions enhance FDI location advantages and increase FDI.

Ouechtati (2020) assesses the nexus between FDI and institutions in ninety developing countries between 2000 and 2016 using panel VAR and finds that institutional shocks had negative effect on FDI in the countries. It was explained further that the factors responsible for negative effect on FDI are lack of access to sound money and instability of property right and legal structure. He also argues that foreign investors were insensitive about institutional shock in developing countries before investing in the countries. Mihaela et al (2018) examine nexus between FDI inflows and institutional quality in developing and developed countries and reveal that institutional quality has positive and significant effect on FDI inflows in developed countries but it has insignificant effect on FDI inflows in the developing countries due to weak institutional quality in these countries.

Though their result show that good governance as an index of institutional quality has a significant effect on FDI inflow in developing and developed countries. They conclude that good governance as an index of institutional quality plays a crucial role in attracting greater FDI inflows into the developing and developed countries. Oladapo, Aberu and Adegboyega (2021) examine the effect of investors' objectives and institutional quality on FDI inflows in African regions for the period 1996 to 2019 using GMM and find that investors' objectives influence FDI inflows in the region, but institutional quality has no influence on FDI inflows in the countries. They conclude that institutional quality was not strong enough to attract FDI inflows to the region, and investors' objectives are the major determining factor that attracts FDI inflows to the countries.

Behera *et al.* (2020) investigate the relationship between FDI inflows and institutional quality in emerging countries for the period 2002 and 2016 using the ARDL-PMG technique and find that FDI inflows have a long-run relationship with institutional quality in these countries. Their result also shows that the direction of causality runs from institutional quality to FDI inflows. Chaib and Siham (2014) investigate the nexus between FDI and institutional quality in Algeria between 1995 and 2011 using VECM and show that there is a long-run relationship between institutional quality and FDI in the country. They also find that economic institutional quality and voice and accountability have a long-run positive influence on FDI in the economy. They conclude that enhancement in strong institutional quality promotes attraction of FDI inflows and a virtuous investment climate in the country. Behera *et al.* (2020) investigate the effect of institutional quality on FDI inflows in South Asia for the period 2002 to 2016 using ARDL-PMG and panel Granger causality techniques and show that institutional quality has a long-run relationship with FDI inflows in the region. They also reveal that short-run causality runs from institutional quality to FDI inflows in some countries in South Asia.

Despite the crucial role that institutional quality plays in FDI inflows, studies are yet to emerge in Nigeria. This paper examines the effect of institutional quality on FDI inflows in Nigeria. This will assist policymakers in knowing the direction of policy to be formulated on the link between FDI inflows and institutional quality.

3.0 Methodology

The objective of this paper is to determine the influence of institutional quality on FDI inflow in Nigeria. Following Chen and Jiang (2023), the association between institutional quality and FDI inflow is specified thus

$$fdi = f(ins) \quad 1$$

Where fdi = FDI inflow and ins = institutional quality

This paper considers six indices of institutional quality, namely: rule of law, government effectiveness, control of corruption, political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, regulatory quality and voice and accountability. The paper also considers per capita income, inflation and trade openness as control variables. Equation 1 is rewritten as follows

$$fdi = f(ins, gdp, inf, tro) \quad 2$$

Where gdp = per capita income, inf = inflation and tro = trade openness

The Equation is expressed in econometric form as thus:

$$fdi_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ins_t + \alpha_2 gdp_t + \alpha_3 inf_t + \alpha_4 tro_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 3$$

Equation 3 serves as an estimated model for this paper. Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag is the technique of analysis for this paper. This technique is sophisticated to capture both the short-run and long-run connection among variables. The ARDL model for this paper is specified below

$$\Delta fdi_t = \vartheta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \vartheta_{1j} \Delta fdi_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^k \vartheta_{2j} \Delta ins_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^k \vartheta_{3j} \Delta gdp_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^k \vartheta_{4j} \Delta tro_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^k \vartheta_{5j} \Delta inf_{t-j} + \delta_{1j} fdi_{t-1} + \delta_{2j} ins_{t-1} + \delta_{3j} gdp_{t-1} + \delta_{4j} tro_{t-1} + \delta_{5j} inf_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad 4$$

This paper uses secondary data from 1996 to 2023. FDI inflow, per capita income, trade openness and inflation were sourced from United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), 2024. Institutional quality indexes were sourced from World Governance Indicator (WGI), 2024.

4.0 Results and Discussion

This paper begins with the results of pre-tests, such as correlation and unit root tests. The results of pre-tests are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	CC	FDI	GDP	GE	INF	PV	RL	RQ	TRO
Mean	-1.037	1.643	2.049	-0.930	12.772	-1.608	-0.993	-0.817	15.305
Median	-1.115	1.726	2.318	-1.020	12.226	-1.874	-1.061	-0.888	14.746
Maximum	0.000	4.088	12.276	0.000	29.298	0.000	0.000	0.000	23.052

Minimum	-1.502	-0.040	-4.162	-1.213	5.388	-2.211	-1.513	-1.293	8.643
Std. Dev.	0.395	0.979	3.387	0.347	5.035	0.671	0.401	0.332	4.171
Skewness	1.967	0.305	0.412	2.164	1.215	1.634	1.513	1.448	0.331
Kurtosis	5.868	2.766	3.021	6.282	5.361	4.288	4.845	4.771	2.927
Jarque-Bera	26.658	0.479	4.393	33.189	12.915	13.886	14.134	12.971	1.789
Probability	0.000	0.787	0.111	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.409
Sum	-27.98	44.363	55.312	-25.12	344.842	-43.41	-26.81	-22.05	413.235
Sum Sq. Dev.	4.047	24.919	298.234	3.127	659.059	11.701	4.175	2.866	452.388

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

Table 1 shows that foreign direct investment, per capita income and trade openness are normally distributed, while control of corruption, government effectiveness, inflation rate, political stability and absence of violence/terrorism, rule of law and regulatory quality are not normally distributed.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	CC	FDI	GDP	GE	INF	PV	RL	RQ	TRO
CC	1.000								
FDI	0.156	1.000							
GDP	-0.321	0.407	1.000						
GE	0.886	0.297	-0.088	1.000					
INF	-0.045	0.178	-0.028	0.018	1.000				
PV	0.774	0.392	-0.148	0.870	0.079	1.000			
RL	0.949	-0.095	-0.459	0.808	-0.103	0.687	1.000		
RQ	0.914	0.244	-0.210	0.822	-0.170	0.695	0.856	1.000	
TRO	-0.262	0.677	0.686	-0.003	0.261	-0.049	-0.479	-0.189	1.000

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

The degree of correlation among the institutional quality indexes is very high. This suggests that if all the indices of institutional quality are considered in the same model, the error of serial correlation will be committed. Therefore, this paper considers the indexes in different models to avoid serial correlation in the models.

Table 3: Unit Root Test

Series	Augmented	Phillips-	DF-GLS Test	Order of
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	Dickey-Fuller test statistic	Perron test statistic	stat	Integration
CC	-2.661*	-6.161***	-6.297***	I(0)
FDI	-1.361	-2.269	-0.2809	I(1)
GDP	-2.665*	-2.682*	-2.715***	I(0)
GE	-5.094***	-5.291***	-5.198***	I(0)
INF	-5.393***	-5.393***	-2.573***	I(0)
PV	-2.596	-2.328	-1.73*	I(1)
RL	-2.327	-5.792***	-2.407**	I(0)
RQ	-2.313	-5.254***	-2.523**	I(0)
TRO	-2.289	-2.393	-1.899*	I(1)

***, **, * means 1%, 5% and 10% significance level.

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

The unit root results in Table 3 show that CC, GDP, GE, INF, RL and RQ are stationary at the level while FDI, PV and TRO are stationary at first difference. The results reveal a mixture of I(0) and I(1) which justified the use of ARDL technique in the paper.

Table 4: ARDL (Short Run Analysis)

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7
Variables							
Δcc_t	0.7614** (2.223)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Δge_t	-	0.590* (1.844)	-	-	-	-	-
Δpv_t	-	-	1.544*** (4.032)	-	-	-	-
Δrl_t	-	-	-	1.103*** (3.797)	-	-	-
Δrq_t	-	-	-	-	1.031*** (3.367)	-	-
Δva_t	-	-	-	-	-	1.516** (-2.286)	-
Δiq_t	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.212** (2.484)
Δgdp_t	-0.161*** (-3.434)	-0.102** (-3.055)	-0.120** (-3.492)	-0.115** (-3.073)	-0.043 (-1.542)		-0.063* (-1.896)
Δinf_t	0.023 (1.158)	0.141*** (4.572)	-0.074* (-2.308)		0.149*** (4.948)	0.068** (3.041)	0.079*** (3.442)
Δtro_t	0.074* (1.831)	0.212*** (5.349)	0.133** (2.939)	0.016 (0.0439)		- 0.091** (-2.319)	0.167*** (4.562)
ect_t	-1.281*** (-8.572)	-0.835*** (-6.042)	-1.029*** (-5.108)	-0.407*** (-5.006)	- 0.711*** (-6.241)	- 0.246*** (-3.942)	- 0.920*** (-5.969)
Adj. R ²	0.787	0.599	0.655	0.594	0.594	0.561	0.604

DW	1.914	2.485	1.628	1.249	2.352	2.309	1.974
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***, **, * means 1%, 5% and 10% significance level.

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

The short run analysis of the results in Table 4 shows that control of corruption, government effectiveness, political stability and absence of violence, rule of law and regulatory quality had significant and positive effect on FDI inflow in Nigeria. In contrast, voice and accountability had a significant and negative influence on FDI inflow. This suggests that factors that drive inflow of FDI into the country are control of corruption, stable political environment, government effectiveness, strengthened rule of law and regulatory quality, while voice and accountability discourage attraction of FDI. This paper also considered institutional quality (i.e. summation of all the indices) and revealed that institutional quality had a significant and positive effect on FDI inflows in the country. This implies that, in the short run, strong institutional quality enhances the volume of FDI inflows in the country.

The short-run analysis further reveals that per capita income had a significant and negative influence on FDI inflow in Nigeria. This indicates that a high per capita income discourages the attraction of FDI inflow due to fear of high-income sustainability in the host country. Foreign investors will prefer a country with cheap labour. Inflation had a significant and positive effect on FDI inflow in voice and accountability, government effectiveness and regulatory quality models, but it had a significant and negative effect in political stability and the absence of violence model. While inflation had an insignificant effect on FDI inflow in the control of corruption and rule of law models. Trade openness had a significant and positive effect on FDI inflow in the control of corruption, government effectiveness, and political stability and absence

of violence models, but it had a significant and negative effect in the voice and accountability model, while an insignificant effect was revealed in the rule of law and regulatory quality models. Despite the mixed results, the speed of adjustment from disequilibrium to equilibrium shows that all the models are restored at equilibrium in the long run, that is, institutional quality has long-run relationship with FDI inflow in the country. The paper also conducted a bound test to ascertain the long-run relationship among the variables, and the result is provided in Table 5.

Table 5: Bound Test

	F-stat	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
Model 1	8.1649	10%	2.2	3.09
Model 2	4.056926	5%	2.56	3.49
Model 3	3.537337	2.50%	2.88	3.87
Model 4	3.872142	1%	3.29	4.37
Model 5	4.58348			
Model 6	3.727023			
Model 7	3.959781			
K		4		

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

The result of the ARDL bound test affirms the long-run relationship among the variables. The F-bound test results are significant for all the models. Aside from the long-run relationship, the individual variable long-run analysis is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: ARDL (Long Run Analysis)

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7
Variables							
fdi _t	-1.281*** (-6.341)	-0.835*** (-4.011)	-1.029** (-3.099)	-0.407 (-1.566)	- 0.711*** (-3.959)	-0.246 (-0.774)	- 0.920*** (-4.213)
cc _t	2.657*** (4.139)	-	-	-	-	-	-
ge _t	-	0.596 (1.115)	-	-	-	-	-
pv _t	-	-	1.054** (2.844)	-	-	-	-
rl _t	-	-	-	1.475* (1.807)	-	-	-
rq _t	-	-	-	-	-1.026 (-1.348)	-	-

va _t	-	-	-	-	-	1.705 (1.690)	-
iq _t	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.120 (1.134)
gdp _t	0.167** (2.437)	-0.197** (-2.461)	0.235 (1.824)	0.052 (0.621)	-0.100 (-1.386)	-0.070 (-1.189)	-0.021 (-0.225)
inf _t	-0.019 (-0.777)	-0.189*** (-3.215)	-0.206** (-2.459)	0.068* (1.967)	- 0.232*** (-3.458)	-0.049 (-0.562)	-0.126* (-1.837)
tro _t	0.182*** (4.191)	0.308*** (4.285)	0.072 (0.944)	0.142** (2.419)	0.228*** (3.923)	0.187** (2.339)	0.236*** (3.444)

***, **, * means 1%, 5% and 10% significance level.

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

The long run analysis of the ARDL results reveals that control of corruption, political stability and absence of violence, and rule of law had significant and positive long run effects on FDI inflow in Nigeria. In contrast, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, voice and accountability had insignificant and positive long-run effects on FDI inflow. This implies that control of corruption, political stability and absence of violence, and rule of law are the major determinants that enhance the attraction of FDI inflows into the country. Per capita income had a significant and positive and negative long-run influence on FDI inflow in models 1 and 2, respectively. Inflation had a significant and positive long-run effect on FDI inflow in model 4 but had the significant and negative long-run effect in models 2, 3, 5 and 7. Trade openness had a significant and positive long-run effect on FDI inflow in Nigeria.

The post (diagnostic) tests were conducted to ascertain the validity of the models estimated and the results of the analysis. The post tests are provided in Table 7.

Table 7: Diagnostic Test

	Normality Test	Serial Correlation LM Test	Heteroscedasticity Test	Ramsey RESET Test
Mode 1	9.0029 (0.011)	0.0506 (0.9509)	0.3084 (0.5845)	3.2167 (0.1065)
Mode 2	0.0718 (0.9647)	0.5973 (0.5731)	0.2128 (0.6309)	0.5992 (0.4587)
Mode 3	1.1455 (0.5639)	0.3570 (0.7163)	1.1937 (0.2869)	5.8512 (0.0519)
Mode 4	1.0319 (0.5969)	1.8248 (0.2161)	0.3672 (0.5510)	1.4630 (0.2543)
Mode 5	1.0570 (0.5894)	1.6148 (0.2467)	0.5262 (0.4762)	0.6154 (0.4493)
Mode 6	0.0240 (0.9880)	0.4890 (0.6304)	0.4013 (0.5332)	5.0800 (0.0507)
Mode 7	2.4772 (0.2897)	1.3990 (0.3013)	0.1492 (0.7031)	0.4047 (0.5405)

Figures in parentheses are p-values

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

The diagnostic test results reveal that all the models are free from serial correlation, heteroscedasticity and well specified, and the variables are normally distributed. The stability test is depicted in Figure 1. This figure shows that all the estimated models are stable.

Figure 1: Stability Test

5.0 Conclusion

This paper investigates the impact of institutional quality on FDI inflow in Nigeria using the ARDL technique of analysis. The findings reveal mixed results in short-run and long-run analysis. The findings show that political stability and absence of violence, government effectiveness, control of corruption, regulatory quality and rule of law (as a measure of institutional quality) had significant and positive short run effect on FDI inflow in Nigeria, but voice and accountability (as a measure of institutional quality) had significant and negative influence. Also, political stability and absence of violence, control of corruption and rule of law had a significant and positive long-run influence on FDI inflow in the country. The error correction term of the ARDL technique reveals that there is a long-run relationship between institutional quality and FDI inflow in Nigeria. This paper concludes that institutional quality plays a crucial role in influencing and attracting the volume of FDI inflow in Nigeria.

5.1 Recommendations

The following recommendations are made considering the study's findings:

- i. The government should further strengthen a corruption-free economy, a well-entrenched rule of law and a stable political atmosphere so that the economy will sustain and attract a huge volume of FDI inflow in Nigeria.

- ii. The government should also ensure the elimination of factors that can be responsible for government ineffectiveness, poor regulatory quality, and voice and accountability for the country to reap the full benefit of attracting FDI into the country.
- iii. The government should ensure strong institutional quality at all times so that foreign investors will be highly optimistic to invest heavily in the country.

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